

ALLITERATION ENHANCES THE BEAUTY AND EFFECTS OF WRITING

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***Abstract:** English language have been already the global language of the world. As a result, people around the world have tendency to learn the language from different corner, specifically literature and translation. Admittedly, the stylistic devices play an important role in literature and translation as far as alliteration is used to make the literary work more beautiful and meaningful. Alliteration is imparting a melodic effect to the utterance, moreover its usefulness spans both poetry and prose. In terms of sound and rhythm, alliteration creates a musical and/or lyrical effect that can enhance the overall experience of reading or listening to the words.*

***Key words:** stylistic device, literature, alliteration, poetry, prose, translation.*

Introduction

Alliteration is a stylistic device in which a series of words experience the repetition of the same consonant sound at the beginning of each word. These words occur either in a row or in quick succession to one another. Alliteration is commonly thought of as a device that uses the same letter at the beginning of a word¹. This is true, but alliteration is a little more than just that. Alliteration depends more on the *sounds* of the combination of beginning letters, rather than just that the same letter is repeated. For example, the sounds that “cat” and “kick” make at the beginning of each word would create alliteration. “Cat” and “ceremony,” on the other hand, would not create alliteration despite starting with the same first letter. More specifically, alliteration is the repetition of consonant sounds in the beginning of words. Assonance is the repetition of vowel sounds, and consonance is the repetition of consonant sounds in any part of the word².

Alliteration is a literary device where two or more words in a phrase or line of poetry share the same beginning consonant sound. The words may be adjacent or separated

¹ Galperin I. Stylistics. Moscow, 1990.

² Yumico Iwata. Creating suspense and surprise in short literary fiction: A stylistic and narratological approach.

by one or more words. One of the primary purposes of alliteration is to emphasize something important that the writer or speaker would like to highlight¹.

Methodology

The main methodology of this article is data collection and comparative method. In order to collect information, a great number of websites and articles have been investigated, at the same time, the findings were recorded to data collection checklist's. The findings have been compared to each other in order to identify the main features of alliteration as a stylistic device.

Results and Discussion

After having investigated several articles, following findings have been found. According to linguistics repeated consonant sounds at the beginning of words placed near each other, usually on the same or adjacent lines. Alliteration can be found in many common phrases. Consider the following examples:

- Peter Piper picked a peck of pickled peppers.
- Sally sells seashells by the sea shore.
- How much wood would a woodchuck chuck if a woodchuck could chuck wood?

Alliteration is commonly used for a variety of reasons. Because alliteration can help to increase audience engagement as well as make a particular phrase or saying more memorable, it is often found in speeches and advertising.

Alliteration Examples

“Maybe she’s born with it. Maybe it’s Maybelline.”

This is a line from Maybelline, a popular makeup company. Almost anyone who’s owned a TV would recognize this line from their cable TV commercial campaigns. The repetition of the “m” sound found in the brand’s name makes it catchy and easily remembered.

Another advertisement was about the ads of petrol. “Put a tiger in your tank” was a slogan created in 1959 by Emery Smith, a young Chicago copywriter who had been given the task to produce a newspaper ad to boost sales of Esso Extra. The tiger wasn’t Smith’s invention. He’d first appeared as a mascot for Esso in Norway around the turn of the 20th century. In this advertisement “t” letter is alliterated.

Barack Obama’s Inaugural Address used alliteration of the “s” sounds in order to pack a punch at the end of this line:

- “We, the people, declare today that the most evident of truths — that all of us are created equal — is the star that guides us still; just as it guided our forebears through Seneca Falls, and Selma, and Stonewall.

¹ <https://literarydevices.com/alliteration/>

Martin Luther King, Jr.'s famous "I Have a Dream" speech uses alliteration of the "kah" sound that the letter "c" makes. This heavy sound helps to emphasize the intensity of what he is trying to convey:

- "I have a dream that my four little children will one day live in a nation where they will not be judged by the color of their skin but by the content of their character."

Abraham Lincoln's speech also is formed by alliteration.

"Four score and seven years ago our fathers brought forth on this continent a new nation..."

Like it is mentioned, alliteration is used both in poetry and in prose. Here are some examples of alliteration being used in works of literature:

The epic poem *Beowulf* contains examples of alliteration in almost every line. In Old English, alliteration was particularly important, especially as a way of passing down the tradition of oral storytelling. Alliteration was one of the key tools for making the works memorable enough to be told over and over again. The Irish poet Seamus Heaney translated *Beowulf* with special attention paid to both the rhythm of the original poem and to the use of alliteration. In just this short excerpt, we can see many repeated sounds, all highlighted in red. In the first line, the "f" sound is repeated in "four", "father", and "fighter". The three sons' names all start the "h" sound—Heorogar, Hrothgar, and Halga. Naming children in an alliterative manner was a popular tradition at the time. In the final line we see repetition of the "b" sound in "balm", "bed", and "battle". These words provide a contrast between "balm" to "battle", and the use of alliteration highlights their [juxtaposition](#).

"He was four times a father, this fighter prince:

one by one they entered the world,

Heorogar, Hrothgar, the good Halga

and a daughter, I have heard, who was Onela's queen

a balm in bed to the battle-scarred Swede."

In **Maya Angelou's** autobiography, *I Know Why the Caged Bird Sings*, alliteration is used to bring some lyrical and poetic life to her prose. As a poet, it is natural that Angelou would bring this lyrical quality to her prose as well. Notice the effects of the "s" and "w" sounds and how they help to evoke emotion:

Up the aisle, the moans and screams merged with the sickening smell of woolen black clothes worn in the summer weather and green leaves wilting over yellow flowers

“From forth the fatal loins of these two foes;
A pair of star-cross’d lovers take their life”

(*Romeo and Juliet* by William Shakespeare)

Shakespeare used alliteration very frequently in his plays and poetry. In this prologue to Act I of *Romeo and Juliet*, Shakespeare uses alliteration in the “f” sound of “from”, “forth”, “fatal”, and “foes”; he also alliterates the “l” sound in “loins”, “lovers”, and “life”. In this alliteration example, the words beginning with the “f” sound are united as words of death and destruction—“fatal” and “foes”—while the words beginning with “l” are all connected to the continuity of life, including “loins” and “lovers”. The alliteration thereby weaves these opposing images together.

“Birches” by Robert Frost has also some examples of alliteration.

“They click upon themselves

As the breeze rises, and turn many-colored

As the stir cracks and crazes their enamel.

Soon the sun’s warmth makes them shed crystal shells

Shattering and avalanching on the snow-crust”

In this excerpt from Robert Frost’s poem “Birches” we can find several instances of the “cr” sound: “cracks”, “crazes”, “crystal”, and “crust”. This use of alliteration is onomatopoeic in that the “cr” sound mimics the sound of ice breaking and trees knocking against each other. Frost creates the feel of a forest of birch trees not only through images, but also in the words he uses to create an aural representation of the sound of the trees.

Conclusion

Alliteration has an important role in writing and speech. Its usefulness spans both poetry and prose. In terms of sound and rhythm, alliteration creates a musical and/or lyrical effect that can enhance the overall experience of reading or listening to the words.

In poetry, alliteration brings life to the recitation of a poem, making it more pleasant both to speak and to listen to. This dual engagement with the words increases the artistry of the poem. This can be extended, also, to marketing jingles. Alliteration enhances the pleasure of reciting the words, making them easier to remember. Alliteration commonly enhances the beauty and effects of writing, whether poetry or prose. In prose, the effect tends to be more about emphasis on important ideas rather in addition to aesthetic value

The list of used literature

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